

METHOD FOR ASSESSING MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF LUNGS IN ACUTE RADIATION IN EXPERIMENT

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Resume. The results obtained from histological preparations prepared from the lungs of white non-native rats, which received acute radiation, showed that, unlike the materials obtained from the control group, various pathological changes of morphological nature are visible in the field of vision. In this regard, the cause of these changes is considered to be acute irradiation of laboratory animals involved in experiments.

Keywords. acute and chronic radiation exposure, rat, experiment, lungs.

Acute radiation disease is a group of clinical syndromes that occur after a short (from a few seconds to 3 days) exposure to penetrating radiation at doses that exceed the average body tolerance of 1 Gy (100 rad). Depending on the total level of doses, power and distribution on the body areas, it can occur with predominant damage to the hematopoietic organs (1-10 Gy), intestines (10-20 Gy), general hemodynamic and toxemic manifestations (20-100 Gy) and cerebral disorders (100 Gy) [2,4,6,8,10,12]. The cause of acute radiation sickness is considered to be γ -neutron, X-ray and γ -, β - radiation arising from a nuclear explosion, regime change or violation of the rules for the operation of nuclear power stationary installations [8]. As a result of exposure to ionizing radiation, an acute damage to the genetic apparatus of cellular structures, hematopoietic structures of the bone marrow, lymphatic system, epithelium of the gastrointestinal tract, skin, lungs and other organs occurs [2,29,31,33]. Radiation disease is a polysystemic disease with a characteristic cyclic development, which is caused by the action of ionizing radiation at doses that exceed the maximum permissible [1,6,8,10,12,34]. Depending on the radiation dose and its distribution in the human or animal body, the timing and causes of their death vary. Depending on the mammal species, death occurs on day 7-30 from the moment of exposure, and the causes of death are more often hemorrhagic syndrome or infectious complications [1,3,5,7,9,11,24]. Ionizing types of radiation include electromagnetic vibrations with a short wavelength, X-rays and γ radiation, flows of α and β particles (electrons), protons, positrons, neutrons and other charged particles.

Depending on the penetrating capacity during external radiation, their penetration into the surface or deep layers of tissues is not excluded, it should

be emphasized that α radiation and X-ray radiation are characterized by high penetrating capacity, β radiation has a lower penetrating capacity [26,28,30,32]. Studies have established that different types of radiation are characterized by different biological activity and degree of danger. The first stage of the influence of radiation is the ionization of atoms, molecules of cellular structures, which is accompanied by functional and organic disorders of organs and systems. The direct effect of radiation on protein structures, the dose of which exceeds the permissible dose, is accompanied by their denaturation, and subsequently undergo decay. At the same time, a violation of physicochemical processes with depolymerization of nucleic acids develops in the affected cell, which leads to an increase in the permeability of the cell membrane.

The cell structures most susceptible to radiation include the chromosomes of the nuclei and cytoplasm [14,16,18,20]. The greatest value is given to the formation of atomic hydrogen, hydroperoxyl radicals, hydrogen peroxide. Free oxidative radicals enter into an enzymatic reaction, during which active sulfhydryl groups are converted into inactive disulfide compounds. The biochemical processes that occur lead to a decrease in the catalytic activity of thiol enzyme systems, which as a result leads to a significant decrease in DNA and RNA in cell nuclei, disrupting the process of their renewal [22,25,27]. Changes in biochemical processes in the nuclei are morphologically expressed by various chromosomal disorders and the entire genetic system of the body. In the cell nuclei affected by radiation, radiotoxins accumulate for some time, disorders of neurohumoral and hormonal processes develop, which also negatively affect metabolic processes. Histamine-like toxic amino acids begin to be produced and accumulated in the body. Tissue intoxication is manifested by clinical symptoms of impaired nervous system functioning, changes in the functioning of internal organs [1,2]. To date, the extent of the effect of acute irradiation on the lungs in the comparative aspect has not been conclusively determined.

The aim of the study was to study the content of products of spontaneous oxidative modification of proteins in the blood serum and lung tissue of rats after local irradiation of the projection area of the lungs with gamma radiation. Material and methods of research. Outbred Wistar rats were used in the experiments. For more than 5 years they have been used in a number of laboratories of the Research Institute of Oncology, their various parameters and, above all, the frequency and spectrum of spontaneous tumors, life expectancy, sensitivity to the action of various carcinogenic agents and other modifying factors have been well studied. In total, 55 mature female rats aged 3-4 months,

with a body weight of 140-160 g were used in the dissertation study. The animals were kept in a barrier-type vivarium under standard light conditions (12/12), at a room temperature of 20-23 ° C and a relative humidity of 54-58%. The rats were in polypropylene cages with a metal lattice lid, no more than 6 animals in a cage. The change of litter (sawdust) and drinking (tap) water was carried out 3 times a week. The usual cleaning of the premises was carried out daily, a complete cleaning of the premises with washing of floors and shelves was carried out 2 times a week.

For the convenience of the comparative evaluation of the obtained materials on the morphological examination of the lungs of white non-native rats that received acute radiation, we considered it advisable to first describe the histological picture of this organ of intact laboratory animals.

The obtained results show that in a macroscopic study of the lungs of white non-bred rats that were not exposed and included in the control group without visible pathological changes.

The results obtained on histological preparations prepared from the lungs of white non-native rats, which received acute radiation, showed that, unlike the materials obtained from the control group, interstitial edema and plasma impregnation (plasmoragia) of the vascular walls, stratification of the stroma, atrophic changes of the intercentral brood duct, uneven full blood vessels and dystrophic changes of epitheliocytes of this organ are visible in the field of vision.

In another histological preparation of the lungs of irradiated rats under a microscope in the field of view, along with the interstitial edema described in the previous histological preparation and plasma impregnation of the vascular walls, stratification of the stroma, atrophic change of the parenchyma, uneven fullness of the vessels and sclerotic changes of the vessels of this organ, lymphocytic infiltration of the organ stroma, as well as atrophy of nephrons, are also visible.

The above conditions are the main morphological signs of pathological changes in the lung stroma of the studied laboratory animals of the first group (acute radiation).

After the evaluation of the results obtained on the detection of morphological changes in the lungs in intact and acute-irradiated laboratory animals, the percentage detected of these parameters in a comparative aspect was studied.

The results showed that all laboratory animals in the control group showed morphological signs without pathological abnormalities.

Conclusion. 1. The results obtained from histological preparations prepared from the lungs of white non-native rats, which received acute radiation, showed that, unlike the materials obtained from the control group, various pathological changes of morphological nature are visible in the field of vision. In this regard, the cause of these changes is considered to be acute irradiation of laboratory animals involved in experiments.

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